

EFIKASNOST SBR TRETMANA U UKLANJANJU ANTIBIOTIKA, DROGA I MIKROPLASTIKE U TRETMANU OTPADNIH VODA

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Rezime

Tratman otpadnih voda je neophodan za zaštitu zdravlja ljudi i životne sredine, dok postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda (PPOV) moraju da se prilagode, kako bi se uklonio širok spektar zagađenja, poput različitih hemijskih supstanci i mikrobiološkog zagađenja, ali i sve strožijim zahtevima za kvalitet efluenta. PPOV obezbeđuju da voda koja se ispušta iz postrojenja za prečišćavanje ispunjava regulatorne standarde za osnovne vrste zagađenja, kao što su masti, šećeri, proteini, nitrati, amonijak ili fosfati. Međutim, savremene analitičke metode pokazuju da PPOV nisu u mogućnosti da uklone neke vrste mikropolutanata, poput lekova, droga, hormona, kontrastnih agenasa, veštačkih zaslađivača ili pesticida. U radu su prikazani rezultati ispitivanja mogućnosti dva PPOV koja koriste SBR tehnologiju (eng. *Sequential Batch Reactor*) za uklanjanje mikropolutanata koji nisu regulisani, kao što su farmaceutske proizvodi, droge ili mikroplastika. Dobijeni podaci su pokazali da se neke supstance mogu vrlo efikasno ukloniti SBR tretmanom (npr. kofein, klaritromicin, teofilin, itd.), sa stopom uklanjanja većom od 90%, dok je za druge ovaj tretman neefikasan (npr. klindamicin-sulfoksid, sotalol, metadon, itd.). Uočena je i ograničena sposobnost SBR tretmana za uklanjanje mikroplastike veličina od 10 do 500 µm. Da bi se postiglo bolje uklanjanje brojnih jedinjenja koja se koriste u svakodnevnom životu, potrebni su dodatni tretmani, koji mogu biti zasnovani na membranskim tehnologijama, unapređenim oksidacionim procesima, primeni novih adsorbenata i drugim metodama.

Ključne reči: tretman otpadnih voda, antibiotici, droge, mikroplastika, SBR tretman

THE EFFICIENCY OF SBR TREATMENT IN REMOVING ANTIBIOTICS, DRUGS, AND MICROPLASTICS IN WASTEWATER TREATMENT

Abstract:

Wastewater treatment is necessary to protect human health and the environment, while wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) deal with a wide range of pollution, such as various chemical substances, and microbial pollution, but also requirements for receiving water types, their possible management, and gradually changing local climate. WWTPs ensure that the water discharged from treatment plants meets the regulatory standards for the basic types of pollution such as fats, sugars, proteins, nitrates, ammonia or phosphates). However, advanced analytical methods show that WWTPs are not able to remove some types of micropollutants, such as medicines, drugs, hormones, contrast agents, artificial sweeteners or pesticides. The present research investigates the possibilities of two WWTPs using Sequential Batch Reactor (SBR) in removing micropollutants which are not in the regulatory lists, such as pharmaceuticals, drugs and microplastics. Obtained data showed that some compounds can be very efficiently removed by SBR treatment (e.g. caffeine, clarithromycin, theophylline etc.), with the removal rate more than 90%, while for some compounds the removal is not observed (e.g. clindamycin_sulfoxide, sotalol, methadone etc.). Limited ability of treatment plants to remove microplastics with a size of 10 to 500 μm has been observed. In order to achieve better removal of numerous compounds used in everyday life, additional treatments are needed, which can be based on membrane technology, advanced oxidation processes, new adsorbents and other.

Keywords: wastewater treatment, antibiotics, drugs, microplastic, SBR treatment

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